

Table S1. The list of fixed parameters

Parameter	Value	Description
$D_{L_{ox}}$	$8 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ ^{1,2}	Diffusion coefficient of ox-LDL
D_M	$1.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ ^{1,2}	Diffusion coefficient of macrophages
$\lambda_{L_{ox} \cdot M_1}$	$5.79 \times 10^{-12} \text{ s} \cdot \text{cell}^{-1}$ ²	Phagocytosis rate of ox-LDL by M1-macrophages
$\lambda_{L_{ox} \cdot M_2}$	$2.39 \times 10^{-12} \text{ s} \cdot \text{cell}^{-1}$ *	Phagocytosis rate of ox-LDL by M2-macrophages
δ_{laden}	$0.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cell}^{-1}$ *	Threshold of lipid laden for proliferation
r_p	0.1 ^{1,3}	Probability of proliferation
δ_{proli}	12 hours *	Threshold of time for macrophage proliferation
δ_{ps}^{M1}	$4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$ *	Threshold of ox-LDL concentration for M1-macrophages to phenotypic switching
δ_{ps}^{M2}	$1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$ *	Threshold of ox-LDL concentration for M2-macrophages to phenotypic switching
δ_{death}^M	$1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cell}^{-1}$ ²	Capability of lipid laden in macrophages
$\lambda_{M \cdot L_{ox}}$	$1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^5 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ^{1,2}	Chemotactic sensitivity parameter about macrophages and ox-LDL
κ	$0.02 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ³	Growth rate of macrophage volume
$d_{S_M \cdot C_E}$	$1.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ^{*,1,2}	Degradation rate of ECM by macrophage-like VSMCs

* indicates the estimated value

Reference

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